

A Comprehensive Review on Green Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles from Different Plant Sources in Photocatalytic Degradation of Reactive Dyes

Poomagal J.*, Jayakumar A., Malarvizhi K., Karthi J.

Pallavan Pharmacy College, Kanchipuram-631501, Tamil Nadu, INDIA

ABSTRACT

In this review we focused on different routes of nanoparticles of copper oxide, which is more attention than any other metal oxide. Copper oxide nanoparticles are used in various fields, especially in nanomedicine and biomedical science. Green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles can be synthesized from natural sources like different plant extracts, which can be used as reductants to avoid environmental hazards and risks connected to highly toxic chemicals and consume high energy. Copper oxide nanoparticles are demonstrated to have strong photo catalytic efficacy against pollutants and toxins as well as water-soluble dyes, which are hazardous in industrial wastewater. These investigations explore green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles from plant extract with preferred properties.

Keywords: Copper oxide nanoparticles, nanotechnology, green synthesis, photocatalytic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Current modern medicinal world has moves towards advanced sophisticated elements in the field of sciences and research industries. In which nanotechnology and nanosciences are enlighten as one of the promising techniques, because of its wide range of applications in the research field (1). Nanoparticles of transition metal oxides have been proved vulnerable part in the field of bio-medicine. Among other metal oxides like gold, silver, iron and zinc, copper oxide nanoparticles are attracted more due to its multifarious application in various fields (2). Synthesis of nanoparticles of copper oxide in different avenues like chemical, physical and biological methods. Chemical and physical methods are having challenges because of toxicity chemicals used in the process, which are responsible for environmental pollution (4).

Year by year expansion of industries are increase the risk of pollution by several types of waste materials are mixed with water resources. Organic dyes are major thread, which are discharged into water bodies.

Proper water treatment can remove water soluble dyes using several methods like photo degradation, chemical oxidation, ion exchange and ozonolysis etc (5). Green chemistry plays a major role in terms of eco-friendly synthesis to ensure reduce the risk of environmental pollution. Fabrication of copper nanoparticles can obtained from different plant sources, micro organisms, fungi and algae. Plant sources are comfortably reducing metal ions into metal atoms at nano size (6). Copper oxide nano particle from plant sources are more stable and effective reductants in photo catalytic degradation. The present study is green synthesized copper nano particles from different plant origins and their photo catalytic degradation activity (7).

Green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles:

Generation of copper oxide nanoparticles by various methods like physical, chemical and biological methods have been demonstrated these methods are briefly divided into two types as bottom up synthesis and top down synthesis. In which bottom up synthesis are building up approaches, while top down synthesis

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

are destructive approaches (8). Green synthesis are biological synthesis or bottom up synthesis, copper oxide nanoparticles are synthesized through ecofriendly, cost effective, safe, stable, and longer shelf life of different plant mediated synthesis.

Preparations of copper oxide nanoparticles using plant extracts are superior to fabrication of copper oxide nanoparticles from micro organisms. This may

have some disadvantages like toxicity of bacteria, isolation of micro organism and incubation process. Hence productions of metal and metal oxides nanoparticles from plant extracts are suitable sources (11). The plant's extracts include a variety of bioactive metabolites, including proteins, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols, and tannins, which serve as stabilizing and reducing agents and lower the levels of metallic salts .

Figure 1. Different approaches for the synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles

Table 1. Several plant extracts employed in the synthesis of CuO NPs and their applications.

Plant	Precursor	Method	Size (nm), Morphology	Application	Reference
<i>abutilon indicum</i>	Copper (II) nitrate trihydrate	Solution combustion method	16.78nm	Photocatalytic, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial activity.	2
<i>Coffee powder, pipernigrum seed, coriandrum sativum</i>	Copper sulfate	Solution based method	Below 100nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity.	3
<i>carica papaya</i>	Copper sulfate	Co-precipitation	140nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity.	4
<i>jasmine sambac</i>	Copper sulfate	Solution-gel	13.4nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity	5
<i>Licorice</i>	Copper(II) nitrate	Thermal method	41.37-56.6nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity.	6
<i>Peganum harmala</i>	Copper sulfate	Thermal method	22-41 nm	Photocatalytic and sonocatalytic degradation activity	7

<i>psidium guajava</i>	Copper acetate monohydrate	Sol-gel	2-6nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity	8
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Copper sulfate	Sol-gel	52-55nm	Anti-bacterial and photocatalytic degradation activity.	15
<i>Sargasam wightii</i>	Copper nitrate hexahydrate	Thermal decomposition	20-30nm	Photocatalytic degradation activity	11
<i>Arundinaria gigantea</i>	Copper nitrate trihydrate	Sol-gel	36nm	Photocatalytic and electrochemical sensor activity	12
<i>Serphidium oliverium</i>	Copper nitrate	Mechanic chemical approach, co-precipitation	1.48 μ m	Photoctalytic degradation activity	13
<i>Tridax procumbense</i>	Copper sulfate	Solution-gel	30 μ m	Photocatalytic degradation and antibacterial activity	14

Table 2. Photocatalytic activity of green synthesis CuO NPs.

Plant	Type Of Dye	Source Condition	Time Period (Min)	Reference
<i>abutilon indicum</i>	Acid black 210 organic dye	Sun light	60	2
<i>Coffee powder, pipernigrum seed, coriandrum sativum</i>	Methylene blue	Sun light	60	3
<i>carica papaya</i>	Coomassie brilliant blue R-250	Sun light	90	4
<i>jasmine sambac</i>	Methylene blue	UV light	120	5
<i>Licorice</i>	Rhodamine-B Dye	UV light	120	6
<i>Peganum harmala</i>	reactive blue 5 dye	Sun light	60	7
<i>psidium guajava</i>	Nile blue (NB) and Reactive yellow 160 (RY160)	Sun light	100 and 120	8
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Congo rod dye	UV light	60	15
<i>Sargasam wightii</i>	Rhodamine B dye, methylene blue, methylene orange	UV light and sunlight	30	11
<i>Arundinaria gigantea</i>	AR 88 dye	UV light	80	12
<i>Serphidium oliverium</i>	Methylene green	sunlight	60	13
<i>Tridax procumbense</i>	Trypan blue textile dye	UV light	48 hours	14

Plants role in green synthesis of CuO NPs:

Plants are having number of physiologically active phyto constituents, so lot of herbals have proved their anti-parasitic, anti-cancer, anti-microbial, fungi static characters and Photocatalytic degradation activities. Since these phyto constituents contain many

polyphenols can perform as both chelating and reducing agent for nanoparticles. The resulting particles are protecting against chain reactions and aggregation.

Flavanoids in plant extract are working directly scavenge molecular species of active oxygen. The

plant extract produce electron which is responsible for reduction of copper salts. The phyto constituents react with copper ion undergoes reduction and converted into copper oxide nanoparticles.

Photocatalytic activity:

Dyes are broadly divided into two categories namely, Natural dyes and Synthetic dyes. Natural dyes are obtained from herbal plant sources as well as from minerals and animal sources. Synthetic dyes are

obtained from laboratory a synthesis which are further classified into three groups. Anionic dyes which are hydrophilic in nature and undergoes direct and reactive dyes. Cationic dyes are basic dyes. Non-ionic dyes are pigment and solvent dyes.

Among the above three dyes the cationic dyes are most poisonous in both type of human and aquatic eco system. So it is essential to remove these dyes from the eco system.

Figure 2. Classification of dyes.

Mechanism of photocatalytic degradation:

The principle involved in photocatalysis is chemical reaction based on the interaction of photons with copper oxide nanoparticles. The mechanism involves few steps in which initially copper oxide nanoparticles direct contact with light and generating electrons and a hole. The photogenerated electrons further reacts with oxygen molecules gives

superoxide free radical. The hole react with water and hydroxyl ions generates highly mercurial hydroxyl radicals, both superoxide free radicals react furiously with cationic dyes and decompose or decolorize it. The rates of reaction of organic dye mainly depend on morphological and crystal structure of photochemical catalyst. Increasing surface area and crystalline structure active site of photocatalyst can be improved.

Fig. 3: Reducing ability of antioxidant phenolics of plant extract to produce nanoparticles

CONCLUSION

In this review different copper precursors for copper nanoparticles were discussed and investigated which revealed that various plants, sizes, morphological and characteristics are sensitive to diverse conditions. Among different methods of nanoparticles, plant mediated nanoparticles include renewable energy, cosmetics, medicines and other essential goods are notable application. In this review articles CuO NPs which can be used to Photocatalytic degradation of cationic dyes which are hazardous to eco system. The application of photocatalyse which copper oxide nanoparticles as an better method than physical and chemical process. Nanocatalyst are affordable price, chemically stable, environmentally friendly and quickly oxidisable. The present days scientist are feeling optimistically to resolve current industrial issues based on enlightened knowledge of the effect of nanoparticles size, shape and their interaction with stabilizing agent. The combo of copper metal on plant mediated photocatalyst were studied in this review will be the promising alternative for efficient Photocatalytic degradation.

Acknowledgements:

Authors are grateful to the management and faculty members of Pallavan Pharmacy College, kancheepuram for providing all necessary outputs to write this review work.

Conflicts of interest:

The author declare that no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Naveen Thakur, Pankaj Kumar, Nikesh Thakur, Kuldeep Kumar, Ashwani Tapwal, Pankaj Sharma, A review of new developments in the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles via plant extracts for enhancing the photo catalytic activity, *Biomaterials and Polymers Horizon* (2022) 1(4).
2. Faheem Ijaz, Sammia Shahid, Shakeel Ahmad Khan, Waqar Ahmad, Sabah, Zaman, Green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using *Abutilon indicum* leaf extract: Antimicrobial, antioxidant and photo catalytic dye degradation activities, *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* April 2017; 16 (4): 743-753.
3. Pratiksha P. Mandrekar¹ and Andrew D'Souza, Green Synthesis Of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles Using Coffee, Piper Nigrum, And Coriandrum Sativum And Its Application In Photocatalytic Degradation Of Methylene Blue Dye, *Rasayan J. Chem.*, 16(1), 276-283, (2023).
4. Renu Sankar, Perumal Manikandan, Viswanathan Malarvizhi, Tajudeennasrin Fathima, Kanchi Subramanian, Shivashangari, Vilwanathan Ravikumar, Green synthesis of colloidal copper oxide nanoparticles using *Carica papaya* and its application in photo catalytic dye degradation, *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 121 (2014) 746–750.
5. Shazia Nouren, Ismat Bibi, Abida Kausar, Misbah Sultan, Haq Nawaz Bhatti, Yusra Safa, Sana Sadaf, Norah Alwadai, Munawar Iqbal, Green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles using *Jasmin sambac* extract: Conditions optimization and photo catalytic degradation of Methylene Blue dye, *Journal of King Saud University - Science* 36 (2024) ,103089.
6. Mohammed Mahmood Masood, Wadhah Naji Jassim Al Sieadi, Photocatalytic Degradation of Rhodamine-B Dye in Wastewater and Biological Study Using Licorice Leave-Mediated Copper Oxide Synthesis Prepared by Green Synthesis Method, *Advanced Journal of Chemistry, Section A*, 2025, 8(6), 1118-1138.
7. Reza Fekri, Seyed-Ahmad Mirbagheri, Lobat Taghavi, Green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles using *Peganumharmala* extract for photocatalytic and sonocatalytic degradation of reactive dye and organic compounds,
8. Jagpreet Singha, vanish Kumarb, Ki-Hyun Kimc, Mohit Rawata, Biogenic synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using plant extract and its prodigious potential for photocatalytic degradation of dyes, *Environmental Research* 177 (2019) 108569.
9. Abderrhmane Bouafia, Salah Eddine Laouini, Mohammed Redha Ouahrani, A Review on Green Synthesis of CuO Nanoparticles using Plant Extract and Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity, *Asian J. Research Chem.* 13(1): January - February 2020

10. Abdul Waris, Misbahud Din, Asmat Ali, Muhammad Ali, Shakeeb Afridi, Abdul Baset, Atta Ullah Khan, A Comprehensive Review of Green Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles and Their Diverse Biomedical Applications, *Inorganic Chemistry Communications* (2020).108369.
11. P. Ramesh , A. Rajendran, Photocatalytic dye degradation activities of green synthesis of cuprous oxide nanoparticles from *Sargassum wightii* extract, *Chemical Physics Impact* 6 (2023) 100208.
12. H.N. Jayasimha, K.G. Chandrappa, P.F. Sanaula, V.G. Dileepkumar, Green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles: A promising material for photocatalysis and electrochemical sensor, *Sensors International* 5 (2024) 100254.
13. Sadia Aroob , Sónia A. C. Carabineiro , Muhammad Babar Taj , Ismat Bibi , Ahmad Raheel ,Tariq Javed, Rana Yahya , Walla Alelwani , Francis Verpoort , Khanita Kamwilaisak , Saleh Al-Farraj and Mika Sillanpää, Green Synthesis and Photocatalytic Dye Degradation Activity of CuO Nanoparticles, *Catalysts* 2023, 13, 502.
14. A. Vetrimani, K. Geetha, E. Angel Jemima, N. Arulnathan, Hyun-Seok Kim and A. Kathalingam, Effect of the green synthesis of CuO plate-like nanoparticles on their photodegradation and antibacterial activities, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 24 (47), 2022.
15. Sumalatha Boddu, Bhanu Prasad Marri , Raveena Malkari Katika , Indira Mikkili , Green Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles (CuONPs) using *Ricinus Communis*: Efficient Photocatalytic Dye Degradation and Antibacterial Applications, *Water Air Soil Pollut* (2025) 236:209.
16. Balkrishna A, Kumar A, Arya V, Rohela, A., Verma, R Nepovimova, E., Krejcar, O., kumar, D., Thakur, N. and Kuca,K., 2021. Phytoantioxidant Functionalized Nanoparticles: A Green Approach to Combat Nanoparticle-Induced Oxidative Stress. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 2021, p. 1-20.
17. A. Musa, A.H. Mohammed, M. Ahmad, M. Musah, Copper nanoparticles synthesized in biopolymer matrix and their application in antibacterial activity, *Baghdad Science Journal*, 2024, 21, 1055-1055.
18. M.A. Atiya, A.K. Hassan, F.Q. Kadhim, Green synthesis of copper nanoparticles using tea leaves extract to remove ciprofloxacin (CIP) from aqueous media, *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 2021, 2832-2854.
19. M. Shafagh, F. Rahmani, N. Delirezh, CuO nanoparticles induce cytotoxicity and apoptosis in human K562 cancer cell line via mitochondrial pathway, through reactive oxygen species and P53, *Iranian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences*, 2015, 18, 993.
20. S.K. Chandraker, M. Lal, M.K. Ghosh, V. Tiwari, T.K. Ghorai, R. Shukla, Green synthesis of copper nanoparticles using leaf extract of *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. and study of their photocatalytic and antibacterial activities, *Nano Express*, 2020, 1.

HOW TO CITE: Poomagal J.*, Jayakumar A., Malarvizhi K., Karthi J., A Comprehensive Review on Green Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles from Different Plant Sources in Photocatalytic Degradation of Reactive Dyes, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 1143-1148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034491>

